

Software Risks for Critical Infrastructure towards 2040: Expert Forecasts - Final Report

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7 October 2024

Executive Summary

This report explores the implications of trends in software development and use between now and 2040 on incidents in UK Critical National Infrastructure (CNI), and what might be done now to address problems. From a two round Delphi study and workshop involving 22 experts in future CNI security, it explores and prioritises trends, major risks, and approaches to address those risks.

The experts forecast increasing Internet of Things (IoT) sensor and control technology, digital-based control, interconnectivity between systems and decentralisation of services. The particularly concerning risks resulting from all these trends are poor responses to incidents; poor human factor design leading to human errors; and wider scope of problems due to shared elements in the supply chain, increased system interdependence and lack of variety in technology.

The experts recommended responding by adding human- and system-centred ‘resilience’ approaches to existing cybersecurity and ‘secure by design’ approaches. Accordingly, we strongly recommend research into sociotechnical cyber resilience best practices to provide UK CNI specialists with the tools they need for the future.

Introduction

The study explored these research questions:

RQ1 What effect may change in the nature and use of software systems between now and 2040 have on the potential for major incidents related to UK Critical National Infrastructure (CNI), especially as related to the Civil Nuclear, Communications, Energy and Health sectors?

RQ2 What actions can we as a society take now to address the resulting risks?

Figure 1: Research Methodology: Two Round Delphi Study

We used a two-round Delphi-style study, as illustrated in Figure 1. It involved multiple interviews with a range of experts in CNI security, policy and technical specialities (see Appendix), recruited through referrals.

From the first round of one-hour interviews, we created an initial short report¹, which was distributed to all participants.

Each expert then completed an online questionnaire with a Likert scale of agreement to each statement in the report; and prioritised the top five risks and mitigation approaches there. They then discussed, in a half hour interview with a researcher, their reasons for anything but complete agreement with each statement and provided suggestions for improvement. The research team selected the most highly prioritised risks and mitigation statements, and summarised the comments for each, then updated the statements to reflect those comments.

We then carried out an in-person workshop, including six of the experts and three specialists in CNI futures from UK government, to gather further insights in how best to present and use the Delphi study information. This report combines results from that workshop with the findings from the two earlier reports.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13255281>

Figure 2: Risks Ranked by Number of Votes

Overview of Results

Each participant selected their top 5 risks out of 19. Figure 2 selects the 9 highest ranked:

Similarly, each participant also selected their top 5 mitigation approaches out of 15. Figure 3 shows the 8 highest ranked.

This report therefore explores 4 statements describing CNI; 12 identified trends; 9 risks selected from a list of 19; and 8 mitigation strategies from a list of 15.

Linking Trends, Risks and Mitigation Strategies

Figure 4 summarises these statements: showing how trends lead to risks, which can be addressed by mitigation strategies. The figure derives from an exercise done independently in three groups at the workshop and shows only the connections identified by at least two of the groups.

The following sections explore the participant responses as four sets of statements: what is CNI, the trends, the risks, and mitigation approaches.

Figure 3: Mitigation Approaches Ranked by Number of Votes

Figure 4: Derivation of Risks from Trends, and Mitigation Strategies from Risks

What is CNI?

Since our research focusses on “UK Critical National Infrastructure”, we needed first to achieve a shared understanding of the nature of software in CNI. The participants broadly agreed on the following points:

1. **Definition of CNI:** Definitions of ‘Critical National Infrastructure’ vary considerably, from ‘sufficient infrastructure to recover from a nuclear attack’ in the UK in the 1950s, to ‘anything politically sensitive’ as appears to be current in the USA; definitions also vary as technology changes. The current official UK definition is of services in thirteen sectors where incidents could lead to major loss of life, casualties, economic or social impacts; or impact national security or state functioning². Much of CNI is in the private sector, and services making up the supply chain to CNI are therefore themselves critical.
2. **Longevity of software:** much CNI software and infrastructure is long lived: up to many decades. It is hard to preserve developer knowledge over those timeframes; that and safety concerns can hinder modernisation and the removal of vulnerabilities.
3. **Commercial drivers:** CNI are operated by public and private sector organizations; commercial visions may impact technology strategies and their implementation. However, innovation is mainly led by government discourse, often through spin-out companies led by people expert in particular CNI domains.

² <https://www.npsa.gov.uk/critical-national-infrastructure-0>

Figure 5: Overview of Fifteen Year Trends

4. **Use regulation to coordinate response to CNI risk:** Organisations in highly regulated sectors, such as nuclear, energy and health, work together with government to provide regulatory bodies, forming an industry consensus on defining their response to risks.

Expert Forecasts - Trends

The experts identified a range of trends affecting the potential for major incidents related to software, as shown in Figure 5. The trends are as follows.

1. **IoT and other next generation technologies:** by 2040 there will be extensive use of Internet of Things (IoT) technology: a network of physical objects embedded with sensors and actuators that connect and exchange data with systems over the internet. These will be supported by Cloud internet processing, and often ‘Digital Twins’, virtual representations of physical systems for monitoring, simulation, and analysis. Rates of adoption will vary by sector; for example, transport is already adopting all of these technologies, whereas utilities and nuclear will take much longer.
2. **System complexity and interconnectivity:** by 2040, CNI software systems will have increasingly complex architectures and increasing connections to other systems, though less so in highly regulated sectors. This will make it more difficult to understand the complex sociotechnical interactions involved—the interplay between humans and technology within each system—and will in some cases—make systems more vulnerable to human error and to attacks.
3. **Increase in digitisation:** Towards 2040, most infrastructure will become software-controlled, to simplify control, increase efficiencies, decrease costs, and provide data accessibility.

4. **Decentralisation of services:** Towards 2040, digitisation will enable the distribution of CNI functions and services away from a central point to various, often remote, locations. Remote communications, wireless and radio technologies will allow the dispersal of functions like electricity generation, perhaps including nuclear in the form of Small Nuclear Reactors. Centralised control will still be the default in most cases.
5. **System operators working through software, not directly:** By 2040 humans' participation in CNI processes will increasingly be through complex software systems rather than directly with hardware or simple software controls; however, analogue systems and direct human participation will still remain, especially in safety-critical systems.
6. **Increased end-user dependency on technology:** 2040 will continue to see increased reliance by consumers on software, data and machines to plan and carry out activities. In CNI, humans will be kept in the loop for critical functions.
7. **Changing geopolitical context:** may impact the Internet and the information it holds by segregating it into separate blocs with differing values and standards, though telecommunications standards will remain global.
8. **Climate change:** will continue to drive digitisation and automation to provide solutions to mitigate harms, such as distributed systems to support greener energy.
9. **New CNI:** Aspects of the internet ('the cloud') have already become critical infrastructure, even if they are not defined as such; this trend will continue with increasing digitisation towards 2040.
10. **Artificial intelligence:** Towards 2040, advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) will open doors to increased and improved automation, better situational awareness, and better data interpretation; as well as the development of safer, more efficient, and more effective systems. However, it will also bring increased risks, such as deep fakes and unpredictability.
11. **Quantum computing:** will not have a major impact by 2040; it will be only for a few international companies and nation states and will be supported by AI techniques. Quantum breaking of cryptographic encryption might be possible then, though easily mitigated by algorithm changes. Quantum techniques for secure communication will be used in some cases.
12. **Off-the-shelf hardware and software:** Towards 2040, some CNI systems will increasingly be made from off-the-shelf hardware and software components. This brings benefits in cost and sometimes reliability, but will bring risks where they are not built to a high enough standard. Many CNI operators will still prefer to develop bespoke systems or to strengthen their off-the-shelf components.

Expert Forecasts - Risks of Major Incidents

This section explores the factors that might lead to a major incident. Software-related risks vary enormously in probability and likely impact; and may relate to malicious actors, human error or both. There will also be 'unknown' risks, yet to be identified. Figure 6 illustrates the risks identified by the survey participants, distinguishing primary 'causes' of incidents from subsequent 'magnifiers' of an incident's impact. The following sections describe each risk.

Figure 6: Identified Risks

1. **Poor response to accidents or attacks:** The response to adverse events is key part of what makes them ‘major’ or otherwise. Though much of CNI is run by well-prepared mature large companies, towards 2040 we shall see increasing difficulty in identifying and responding due to:
 - a. Poor human response due to lack of training, lack of sharing of key information, trust in bad quality data, lack of government-led preparation and poor human factor aspects of systems;
 - b. New forms of malicious activity as actors become more sophisticated; or
 - c. Issues with AI-based situational awareness and guidance.
2. **Attacks via Humans:** Towards 2040, most cyberattacks will continue to involve humans and machines: both insider threats and external attackers focusing on human vulnerabilities such as taking advantage of weak passwords or manipulating people into taking inappropriate actions, even when the software works as specified. Improvements in social engineering techniques and deep fake technology will exacerbate this problem.
3. **Cascading Problems:** Towards 2040, increased interconnectivity, due to extensive use of IoT, will mean that minor problems or failures in non-essential elements will sometimes escalate and affect wider, vital aspects of a system. The complexity of systems will make it difficult to identify such vulnerabilities in advance.
4. **Software and hardware supply chain problems:** 2040 will continue to see increasing issues with the provision of software components, software services, hardware supplies, system maintenance and related services. This will be exacerbated by the international nature of such supply chains, despite work being done to map and understand them. Further obstacles will include the disconnect between technology users and developers, the disconnect between procurement and technical specialists, as well as conflicts with the commercial interests of suppliers.

5. **Sociotechnical problems:** By 2040, digitisation, increased complexity and poor human factors in design of systems (a term that includes the operators and users), will lead to increasing disruptions—even when all the participants are working in good faith³.
6. **Breakdown of electricity, telecommunications or internet:** By 2040, much of CNI will not be able to function without these. Electricity in particular is easy to disrupt, and failure may cause cascading problems. For example, a widespread loss of electricity supply would prevent delivery of all of transport, communications, health services, food, and other critical services.
7. **OT attacks:** Operational Technology (OT)—the systems that monitor and control physical processes, particularly in industries like manufacturing, energy, and utilities—used to be relatively safe from cyberattack because of the obscurity of its programming and the isolation of OT systems. However, towards 2040, OT will increasingly be integrated with Information Technology and IoT technology, making it easier for cyber attackers, especially nation states, to connect and disrupt electromechanical systems.
8. **AI-based phishing, whaling and similar attacks:** Towards 2040, generative AI will be widely used in cyber-attacks where individuals are tricked into divulging confidential information or installing malware. ‘Whaling’, which targets high-profile individuals, will be particularly affected.
9. **Common mode failures:** Towards 2040, widely dispersed systems will increasingly have monoculture technologies (systems, components and vendors) for portions of their operations, which will thus share the same vulnerabilities. These will allow mass replicated attacks or lead to cascading problems.

Mitigation Strategies

Our experts suggested a range of complementary approaches to address the future risks they identified, as illustrated in Figure 7. Such ‘mitigation approaches’ address and reduce the wider problem in addition to improving defences and the response to incidents. The following sections explore each mitigation suggested.

1. **Systems Resilience approach:** Designing and organising to provide *resilience* in addition to cybersecurity: the capacity to endure and adapt to disruptions. Resilience is a feature of an entire system (of systems); addressing it might involve incident planning, red teaming, redundancy in provision, design for gradual degradation and enforcement of systems diversity. Resilience research can include systems thinking and actor network theory.
2. **Secure systems by design (SSBD):** Incorporating systems security, privacy and safety analysis—including human interaction analysis—from the earliest stages of design in creating and modifying software systems rather than later in the development cycle. By focusing on individual products and components, SSBD delivers layers of security, provides a path for upgrades, and can be applied to enhancements to existing systems.
3. **Improved risk management:** Supporting organisations to systematically identify, understand, and assess potential threats, integrating these practices into both system design and ongoing processes, to support focusing on risks with a high expectation of loss

³ As happened in the Three Mile Island and Chernobyl incidents.

Figure 7: Mitigation Strategies

rather than just high probability. While well-established in finance and healthcare, risk management needs broader adoption in other industries to enhance cybersecurity resilience, with an appropriate light touch to avoid it becoming costly and unwieldy.

4. **Training of professionals:** ensuring consistent education of software and domain expert professionals in both theoretical and practical aspects of security and resilience across all levels, including the implications for software contracts to define responsibilities and liabilities around cyber risks.
5. **Research into Sociotechnical approaches:** Research and research dissemination covering the human, non-technological, aspects of CNI system security, software design and user interfaces. Though this research is difficult for traditional cybersecurity researchers, and subject to bias and replication problems.
6. **Adversarial systems testing including red teaming:** While 'Penetration Testing' only explores weaknesses in the software, 'Red Teaming' involves cybersecurity experts simulating attacks on the whole system, including human users and support staff. Techniques include both ethical hacking, and social engineering approaches.
7. **Legislation, regulation and government support for resilience:** to motivate organisations to invest in systems resilience, secure by design approaches and adversarial systems testing. Effective tools tend to be regulations supported by laws, and industry standards and implementation guides.
8. **Education of end users:** Training for end users at all levels about the dangers of AI-enhanced 'phishing' and about what digitalisation means for their roles. While no substitute for appropriate human factors and system design, this can reduce the immediate risk.

Workshop Findings

The in-person workshop derived the following additional insights:

1. **Interlinking:** We are getting faster at making things complex and interconnected; this is a design philosophy rather than inherent in the situation. We are building layers of legacy systems.
2. **Recovery:** Wholistic recovery approaches are needed, using systems thinking and based on resilience studies incorporating human factors.
3. **Human Impact:** The human impact of incidents is frequently neglected: technical recovery is often the focus, but societal recovery, such as getting people home from stranded trains, is often the main problem.
4. **Risk Ownership:** Corporate perception of risk is limited to the financial and direct impact on the organisation; the true risks to society are typically much higher.
5. **Legislation:** This should not be viewed as a form of mitigation but rather as a tool for implementing mitigation strategies. Key is the regulations and standards beneath the overarching laws.
6. **Labels:** Labels determine access to resources: a ‘cyberattack’ gets more support than an ‘accident’; ‘secure by design’ gets extra up-front spending.
7. **Regulations:** A popular suggestion was to modify existing regulations rather than create new ones; promote management regulations over technical ones; and establish unified standards for industry best practices.
8. **Research:** In terms of research, a consensus identified a need for wholistic studies, involving a human-centred, systems-based view around resilience and recovery.

Conclusion

Throughout this project, as researchers we have been impressed by the level of cybersecurity skills and governance apparent in each of the CNI sectors touched upon. There appears to be a strong understanding both of the risks each sector faces and of cost-effective approaches to addressing those risks. This confirms the implied assumption of an acceptable status quo, in asking a question specifically about change:

RQ1 What effect may change in the nature and use of software systems between now and 2040 have on the potential for major incidents related to CNI...?

To our surprise, the expert opinions focussed less on changes to the technical causes of major incidents—such as AI-enhanced attacks—and more on the increasing consequences of such incidents and reducing capacity of the combined human and software (‘sociotechnical’) systems to fully recover. So, while we anticipate increasing sophistication in attacks (especially via humans), two of the top three risks were poor responses to successful cyberattacks, and cascading problems where one failure leads to more.

So, turning to RQ2, *What actions can we as a society take now to address the resulting risks*, the survey clearly identifies a need for research to develop ‘tools’ for sociotechnical cyber ‘resilience’: a need for approaches that use a combined human and machine view to find ways to make services that can both recover effectively from cyberattacks and reduce their impact.

Research into sociotechnical cyber-resilience is vital to prepare CNI organisations and ecosystems for the future.

Appendix: Table of Participants

Table 1 is an anonymised list of our participants. P1 and P2 from the pilot study are omitted. The third column estimates their professional experience in years, including postgraduate research; the fourth their current country. P8, P15, P21, P22 and P24 identify as female; the others as male. Columns 'Nuclear' through 'Government' indicate specific areas of CNI expertise for each participant (colours distinguish columns). Column 'CNI' indicates where a participant has expertise related to CNI cybersecurity in general; and the rightmost column indicates where they have professional experience with regulation or government policy on CNI topics.

Table 1: Project Participants

ID	Description (role and specialism)	Experience (yrs.)	Country	Nuclear	Energy	Telecoms	Health	Transport	Internet	Military/Defence	Emergency Services	Government	CNI	Regulation/Policy
P3	Academic specialising in cybersecurity and resilience of networked systems.	26	UK											
P4	Government scientist specialising in security of software systems.	26	UK											
P5	Government scientist specialising in security of nuclear systems.	39	USA											
P6	Academic leading major group covering cyber security and advanced computing.	33	Austria											
P7	Academic leading group researching future digital resilience.	24	UK											
P8	Human factors and cybersecurity expert working in the rail industry.	20	UK											
P9	Industry program director working on digital twins.	27	UK											
P10	Academic leading (different) research project into future CNI risks.	26	UK											
P11	Independent OT cyber security consultant, working with industry and government.	44	UK											
P12	Academic leading cyber futures research institute.	9	USA											
P13	Academic, from industry, specialising in future health informatics.	28	UK											
P14	Academic specialising in impact from research related to National Security including future cybersecurity risks.	40	UK											
P15	Academic and consultant specialising in emergency management.	16	UK											
P16	Academic specialising in cybercrime relating to emerging technology.	30	Canada											
P17	CEO of industry consultancy specialising in OT cybersecurity	15	UK											
P18	Consultant in engineering and regulation to industry and government.	40	UK											
P19	Academic expert in computer networking and resilient systems.	46	UK											
P20	Academic specialising in international security, especially cyber warfare.	13	UK											
P21	Researcher specialising in cyber policy and national security.	5	UK											
P22	Author and industry consultant expert at future study and software.	55	UK											
P23	Senior academic specialising in cybersecurity, law and future technologies.	24	USA											
P24	Researcher studying future resilience and sustainability.	5	UK											